

***ortho*-Amino-phenylhydrazine and some Interesting
Hetero-cyclic Compounds derived from it. Part III.
Lengthened *o*-Di-derivatives of Benzene and
their Ring-closure.**

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In Part I, Guha and Ray (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 86) have shown that 1-*ortho*-nitrophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide $C_6H_4(NO_2).NH.NH.CS.NHPh$, on reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid, gives 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide, which in presence of strong hydrochloric acid loses a molecule of ammonia to yield 2-phenylimino-5:6-benzo-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-1:3:4-thiadiazine. The present investigation was undertaken with the object of utilising the reactive amino group of several aminophenylthiosemicarbazides by condensing with thiocarbimides, carbimides, potassium cyanate, thiocyanate and aldehydes and study the effect of diverse types of ring-closing agents upon the lengthened *ortho*-diderivatives of benzene thus obtained.

o-Nitrophenylhydrazine has now been condensed with tolyl, xylyl and allyl mustard oils to yield three 4-substituted-1-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazides (I, IV, VII). 1-Nitrophenyl-4-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide and 1-nitrophenyl-4-xylyl-thiosemicarbazide on reduction give two compounds in each case, *vis.*, 1-aminophenyl-4-tolylthiosemicarbazide (II) and 1-tolyl-2:3-benzo-6-thiol-1:4:5-triazine (III), 1-aminophenyl-4-tolylthiosemicarbazide (V) and 1-xylyl-2:3-benzo-6-thiol-1:4:5-triazine (VI); whereas, from the allyl compound only the corresponding aminophenylthiosemicarbazide (VIII) has been obtained, thus :

The triazine constitution * of the above ring-closed compound follows from the fact that they are soluble in cold dilute alkali, give disulphides with iodine, and insoluble mercaptides with mercuric chloride.

1-*o*-Aminophenyl-4-phenyl, (tolyl, xylyl)-thiosemicarbazide gives the corresponding thiol-triazine compounds when treated with acetic anhydride and strong hydrochloric acid, showing conclusively that during reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid, the nitro group is first reduced to amino which loses ammonia to give rise to the thiol-triazines. Evidently, the ring closure is effected thus:—

Guha (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1036) obtained di-*R*-iminothiobiazoles from hydrazinedicarbothioamides by the action of acetic anhydride when H_2S was spilt off (compare also Guha and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 162) who obtained alkylthiolaryliminothiobiazoles from thiosemicarbazide-dithiocarboxylates by the elimination of one molecule of sulphuretted hydrogen. It is peculiar that in the present instance ammonia is spilt off instead of sulphuretted hydrogen.

The following lengthened *ortho*-di-derivatives of benzene have been obtained from *o*-amino-phenyl-4-*R*-thiosemicarbazides by the action of phenyl-, tolyl-, xylyl- and allyl-thiocarbimides.

* The benzo-thiadiazine constitution assigned to this compound by Guha and Ray (*loc. cit.*) has now been found to be wrong. It possesses a mercaptanic group due to the presence of which it is soluble in alkali and gives a disulphide. The description of the properties of this substance as given in Part I of this paper is rather inexplicable. It was through some sort of mistake, perhaps, that the properties of some other substance were attributed to this compound.

1-Tolylthiocarbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbazido-benzene (X) yields on treatment with strong hydrochloric acid 2-tolylamino-4:5-benzo-8-thio-1:3:6:7-octathiotriazine (XIV), thus:—

The alternative dimercaptanic formula

is also possible. By analogy with the formation of amino-thiol-triazole by the ring-closing action of hydrochloric acid upon similar dicarbo-thioamides (Freund and Imgart, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 946; Guha, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 1502) the above constitution has been assigned to the compound (XIV).

1-o-Aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide reacts readily with potassium cyanate and phenyl isocyanate to yield 1-carbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbazido-benzene (XV) and 1-phenylcarbamido-2-phenyl-thiosemicarbazido-benzene (XVI) respectively.

The ring-closure of the above type of lengthened *ortho*-di-derivatives of benzene with strong hydrochloric acid and potassium hydroxide solution gives rise to the identical poly-membered heterocyclic compound, *vis.*, 2:3-benzo-6-phenylamino-9-keto-1:4:5:7-octatetrazine (XVII) thus:—

The above compound (XVII) is acidic in character, possibly due to the presence of the grouping (-CO-NH-) and dissolves in alkali to form sodium salt. It is worth mentioning that no such ring-closure of *ortho*-derivatives of benzene containing the carbonamido and thiocarbonamido groupings is known and it is for the first time that such ring closures have been studied. Freund and Schander (*Ber.*, 1896, **29**, 2506) brought about the ring-closure of the hydrazide $\text{NH}_2\text{CS.NH.NH.CONH}_2$ with hydrochloric acid and obtained imino-thiobiazolone. The action of caustic alkalis upon this type of compounds has been found to effect ring-closure not through a sulphur atom but through nitrogen (Arndt, Milde and Tschenscher, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 841). So it is really interesting to note that it is immaterial whether the ring-closing agent is an alkali or an acid, the result in the present instance is the same. The natural conclusion to be drawn from the above results is that though different types of ring-closing agents exert their individual influences, the substances undergoing ring-closure have also got some influence upon the course of these reactions.

Ferric chloride exerts its oxidising action upon *o*-aminophenyl-4-*R*-thiosemicarbazides and forms 3:4-benzo-7-phenylamino-1:2:5:6-thioheptatriazine (XVIII) and 6:4-benzo-7-tolylamino 1:2:5:6-thioheptatriazine (XIX) thus:—

Fromm, Layer and Nerz (*Annalen*, **433**, 1) obtained di-*R*-imino-thio-biazoles by the action of ferric chloride upon hydrazodithiocarbonyl amides.

Hydrazine hydrate has also been found to effect the ring-closure of *o*-aminophenyl-4-*R*-thiosemicarbazides and thus 1-phenyl-3:4-

of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride from 10 g. of the starting material, whereas the older method gave only 1.5 g. The yield of the thiol-benzotriazine has also been raised to 1 g. as against 0.4 g. by the older method.

The free Base, $\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH.NH.CS.NHPh}$.

The free base was obtained by dissolving the hydrochloride (1 g.) in the least quantity of water and by adding a few drops of sodium carbonate solution to make it just alkaline. A brownish white flocculent mass was thus obtained which was extracted by shaking with ether. The ethereal solution on evaporation yielded a brownish white crystalline mass which was crystallised from alcohol in brownish-white plates, m.p. 102-103°; yield 0.5 g. (Found: N, 21.58. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{S}$ requires N, 21.70 per cent.).

Improved Method of Isolation of Phenyl benzo-thiol-triazine.

The pasty semi-solid mass (compare (ii), *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 92, 5th line) was suspended in water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid and the tarry matter was removed by passing steam through the liquid for two hours. The hot liquid was then further boiled with animal charcoal for half-an-hour and was filtered hot. The solution on cooling and on standing for some time gave beautiful shining white needles, m.p. 151°. It is soluble in hot water, strong hydrochloric acid and cold dilute alkali from the solution of which it can be precipitated by acids.

The Disulphide. - An alcoholic solution of iodine was added drop by drop to an alcoholic solution of the thiol-triazine compound until the solution became reddish-brown in colour. The disulphide was obtained as a yellowish white amorphous powder by the addition of an excess of water to the alcoholic solution. The precipitate was repeatedly washed with a solution of iodine in potassium iodide, with water and finally with alcohol. It was crystallised from methyl alcohol in yellowish white needles, m.p. 175-176°. (Found: S, 13.54. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ requires S, 13.33 per cent.).

*1-*o*-Nitrophenyl-4-*p*-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide (I).*

An alcoholic solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine (10 g.) was heated under reflux on the water-bath with *p*-tolyl-mustard oil (9-10 g.) for about 40 minutes when a yellowish white precipitate was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 176°; yield

is almost quantitative. It is insoluble in water and acids. (Found: S, 10.91. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires S, 10.59 per cent.).

Reduction of Compound (I): Formation of 1-o-Aminophenyl-4-p-tolyl-thiosemicarbazide (II) and 1-tolyl-2:3-benzo-6-thiol-1:4:5-triazine (III).—The method of procedure was the same as followed in the case of the corresponding phenyl compounds (Part I, *loc. cit.*). The aminophenyl-thiosemicarbazide was purified by adding ether to an alcoholic solution of the substance when it was obtained as a white shining crystalline product, m.p. 252-253° with decomposition and producing a blue colouration. It turns reddish-brown on exposure to the air for some time. (Found: S, 10.67. $C_{14}H_{16}N_4S$ requires S, 10.39 per cent.).

Purification of Compound (III).—It was purified as the corresponding phenyl compound and was finally crystallised from water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid in beautiful light yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 182°. It is soluble in cold dilute alkali from which solution it can be precipitated by acids. (Found: N, 16.21. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N, 16.47 per cent.).

The Disulphide of Compound (III) was prepared by the addition of an excess of an iodine solution to an alcoholic solution of the substance and then precipitating it with an excess of water. It melts at 97-98° with decomposition.

Action of Acetic Anhydride upon (II): Formation of 1-Tolyl-2:3-benzo-6-thiol-1:4:5-triazine (III).—1-o-Aminophenyl-4-p-tolylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (1 g.) was heated with acetic anhydride (4 c.c.) on a sand-bath under reflux till a clear brownish coloured solution was obtained. The reaction mixture was then poured into cold water and thus a slight yellow precipitate was obtained and a second crop was obtained by concentrating the mother-liquor. The product was then crystallised from water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid, in light yellow needles melting at 182°. (Found: N, 16.23. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N, 16.47 per cent.). The identity of this compound with (III) was proved by taking the mixed melting point.

1-o-Nitrophenyl-4-(1:3:4)-xylyl-thiosemicarbazide (IV).—An alcoholic solution of o-nitrophenyl hydrazine (10 g.) and xylyl-mustard oil (11 g.) was heated on a water-bath under reflux for about an hour when a yellow crystalline product came out of the solution. The product was further crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 112°; yield

about 19 g. (Found: S, 10.51. $C_{11}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires S, 10.12 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of 1-o-Aminophenyl-4(1:3:4)-xylyl-thiosemicarbaside (V) and 1-Xylyl-2:3-benzo-6-thiol-1:4:5-triazine (VI).—The reduction was carried out by following the methods as adopted in the case of the phenyl and tolyl compounds. The thiosemicarbaside (V) was purified by adding ether to an alcoholic solution of the substance when a white shining crystalline mass was obtained which melted at 255-256° with decomposition and producing a blue colouration. It turns reddish-brown on standing. (Found: S, 10.27. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2S$, HCl requires S, 9.94 per cent.).

The benzo-triazine compound was purified similarly as the corresponding phenyl compound and was crystallised from water slightly acidified with hydrochloric acid in shining white plates, m.p. 173-174°. (Found: N, 15.43. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2S$ requires N, 15.61 per cent.).

Action of Acetic Anhydride upon Compound (V): Formation of 1-Xylyl-2:3-benzo-6-thiol-1:4:5-triazine (VI).—The usual method of preparation was adopted in this case and the resulting product was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in white shining plates, m.p. 173-174°. (Found: N, 15.45. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2S$ requires N, 15.61 per cent.).

1-o-Nitrophenyl-4-allyl-thiosemicarbaside (VII).—An alcoholic solution of *o*-nitrophenylhydrazine (10 g.) and allyl mustard oil (7 g.) was heated under reflux on a water-bath for two hours. On pouring the reaction mixture to cold water (200 c.c.) a yellow crystalline product separated out which was further purified by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 160°. It is insoluble in water and acids but readily soluble in alkali producing a beautiful bluish violet colouration. (Found: N, 22.42. $C_{10}H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.).

Reduction of Compound (VII): Formation of 1-o-Aminophenyl-4-allyl-thiosemicarbaside (VIII).—1-o-Nitrophenyl-4-allyl-thiosemicarbaside (10 g.), granulated tin (10 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (80 c.c.) were heated on a water-bath for three to four hours. The contents of the flask were then largely diluted with water and tin removed by passing sulphuretted hydrogen repeatedly. The solution was evaporated almost to dryness on the water-bath which on cooling yielded a brownish red crystalline mass. The raw product

thus obtained was purified by adding ether to an alcoholic solution of the substance when white shining crystals, m.p. 247-248° with decomposition were obtained. It turns reddish-brown on standing for some time. (Found: S, 12.15. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S$, HCl requires S, 12.40 per cent.).

1-Phenylthiocarbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbasido-benzene (IX).—An alcoholic solution of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) and phenyl mustard oil (1 g.) was heated on the water-bath under reflux for three hours. The reaction product on being poured into water gave a white solid which was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining white rectangular plates, m.p. above 290°. It is soluble in hot water and in cold concentrated alkali; yield 2 gms. (Found: S, 16.48. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires S, 16.29 per cent.).

1-p-Tolylthiocarbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbasido-benzene (X).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the preceding compound (IX). From 2 g. of 1-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride and 1 g. of *p*-tolyl-mustard oil about 2 gms. of the product were obtained. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in shining white plates which did not melt even at 290°. (Found: S, 15.28. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires S, 15.72 per cent.).

1-Xyllythiocarbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbasido-benzene (XI).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the two preceding compounds. The yield of the product was 1.2 g. from 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride and xyllyl mustard oil (0.7 g.). It was crystallised from alcohol in white shining plates which did not melt even at 290°. (Found: S, 15.88. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires S, 15.20 per cent.).

1-Allylthiocarbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbasido-benzene (XII).—The method of preparation was the same as the preceding compound. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white shining plates which did not melt even at 290°; yield 1 g. (Found: S, 18.23. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires S, 17.92 per cent.).

1-p-Tolylthiocarbamido-2-p-tolylthiosemicarbasido-benzene (XIII).—The reaction product was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white shining plates, m.p. 281-282°. (Found: S, 15.55. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires S, 15.21 per cent.).

Action of strong Hydrochloric Acid upon 1-p-Tolyl-thiocarbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbasido-benzene: Formation of 2-Tolylamino-4:5 benzo-8-thio-1:8:6:7-octathiotriazine (XIV).—1-*p*-Tolylthiocarba-

mido-2 phenylthiosemicarbazido-benzene (1 g.) was heated under reflux with concentrated hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19). After about 20 minutes' heating the substance went into solution and on continuing the heating for another 20 minutes, white shining crystals began to come out of the solution. The solution was allowed to cool, filtered, precipitate washed with water and was finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 200°. It is insoluble in water but it readily dissolves in cold dilute alkali. The presence of aniline in the acid filtrate was tested by diazo reaction and coupling with β -naphthol. (Found: N, 17.52. $C_{11}H_{11}N_4S$, requires N, 17.83 per cent.).

1-Carbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbasido-benzene (XV).—Potassium cyanate (0.3 g.) dissolved in the minimum quantity of water was added slowly to 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (1 g.) also dissolved in the smallest quantity of water under cooling. The reaction took place at once and a white solid mass came out which was filtered, washed with water and finally crystallised from dilute alcohol in brownish white plates. It did not melt even at 290°; yield 0.8 gm. (Found: N, 23.02. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_4S$ requires N, 23.25 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid upon (XV): *Formation of 2:3-Benzo-6-phenylamino-8-keto-1:4:5:7-octatetrasine* (XVII).—Two gms. of the compound (XV) were heated with strong hydrochloric acid (50 c.c.) under reflux for about an hour and the reaction product was poured into water when a brownish white crystalline mass came out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in brownish white shining plates, m.p. 145°; yield 1.3 g. (Found: N, 25.99. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_6$ requires N, 26.21 per cent.).

Treatment of Compound (XV) *with 20% Potassium Hydroxide Solution: Formation of Compound* (XVII).—Two g. of the compound (XV) were heated with about 40 c.c. of the potassium hydroxide solution for an hour and a half. The clear solution thus obtained was neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid under cooling when sulphuretted hydrogen was profusely evolved with the separation of a brownish white crystalline mass which was twice crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 145°. (Found: N, 25.64. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_6$ requires N, 26.21 per cent.). The identity of this compound with the preceding one was confirmed also by taking a mixed melting point.

1-Phenylcarbamido-2-phenylthiosemicarbasido-benzene (XVI).—Phenylisocyanate (0.6 g.) was slowly added under cooling to 1-*o*-

aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (2 g.) dissolved in water and the mixture was shaken vigorously for about ten minutes. The reaction took place with the evolution of heat and a brownish flocculent mass separated out which was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. above 290°. (Found: N, 18.82. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$, S requires N, 18.56 per cent.).

Action of Ferric Chloride upon 1-Aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide: Formation of 3:4-Benzo-7-phenylamino-1:2:5:6-thioheptatriazine (XVIII).—Excess of ferric chloride solution was added to 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide hydrochloride (2 g.) when the solution turned reddish brown; the solution was then heated to boiling for about an hour and filtered hot. The crystalline product thus obtained was crystallised from water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid as red needles, m.p. 140°. It was the hydrochloride of a base as was proved by the fact that it gave silver chloride with silver nitrate solution. It is excessively soluble in cold water. (Found: N, 19.21; Cl, 11.54. $C_{13}H_{11}N_4S$, HCl requires N, 19.17; Cl, 11.98 per cent.).

3:4-Benzo-7-p-tolylamino-1:2:5:6-thioheptatriazine (XIX).—The method of preparation was the same as in the case of the compound (XVIII). It was crystallised from water slightly acidulated with hydrochloric acid in beautiful reddish brown needles which did not melt even at 290°. It is very soluble in water and gives silver chloride with silver nitrate solution. (Found: N, 18.29; Cl, 11.21. $C_{14}H_{13}N_4S$, HCl requires N, 18.30; Cl, 11.43 per cent.).

Action of Hydrazine Hydrate: Formation of 1-Phenyl-3:4-benzo-7-thiol-1:2:5:6-heptatriazine (XX).—An alcoholic solution of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) and hydrazine hydrate (0.4 g.) was heated under reflux for about an hour. The solution on cooling gave a brownish white crystalline mass which was filtered, washed with alcohol and then with water and was crystallised from alcohol as white shining plates, m.p. 83-84°. It is soluble in hot water and in cold dilute alkali and gives an amorphous yellow disulphide with iodine solution and a yellowish white mercaptide with mercuric chloride. (Found: N, 22.09. $C_{13}H_{11}N_4S$ requires N, 21.87 per cent.).

1-Allyl-3:4-benzo-7-thiol-1:2:5:6-heptatetrasine (XXI).—The method of preparation was the same as that of the preceding compound (XX). The reaction product was crystallised from alcohol,

m.p. 81-82°. It was soluble in hot water and in cold dilute alkali. It gave an amorphous disulphide with iodine solution and a yellowish white mercaptide with mercuric chloride. (Found: N, 15.29. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2S$ requires N, 25.45 per cent.).

1-Benzalanilino-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (XXII).

A dilute alcoholic solution of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) and benzaldehyde (0.7 g.) was heated on a water-bath under reflux for two hours. Some alcohol was then distilled off and the residual solution on dilution with water gave a white solid mass. Any unconverted benzaldehyde was removed with steam and the solution was filtered hot which on cooling yielded a white crystalline mass which was crystallised from boiling water in white needles, m.p. 168-169°; yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 16.33. $C_{20}H_{15}N_2S$ requires N, 16.18 per cent.).

*1-*o*-Nitrobenzalanilido-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide* (XXIII).—A dilute alcoholic solution of 1-*o*-aminophenyl-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (2 g.) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1 g.) was heated on a water-bath under reflux for 2-3 hours. On cooling greyish white crystals gradually came out of the solution which were filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid as brownish white needles, m.p. 260°. It is sparingly soluble in hot water, readily soluble in acetic acid, acetone and alcohol; yield 1.5 g. (Found: N, 17.79. $C_{20}H_{11}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 17.9 per cent.).

Action of Ferric Chloride upon (XXIII): *Formation of 2-Anilino-5:6-benzo-6-nitrophenyl-1:3:4:7-thio-octatriazine* (XXIV).—1-Nitrobenzalanilido-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (1 g.) was heated with an excess of ferric chloride solution (2 g. dissolved in 18 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid) for about an hour and the solution was filtered hot. On cooling, the filtrate gave beautiful shining brownish coloured crystals which were filtered, washed repeatedly with water and was crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m.p. 216-217°. It gave silver chloride with silver nitrate solution. (Found: N, 16.83. $C_{20}H_{11}O_2N_2S$, HCl requires N, 16.47 per cent.).

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